

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

HOW TO DEVELOP SOFT AND HARD SKILLS THROUGH THE USE OF STEM

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Abstract

A high need for early purposeful development of students' skills in computational thinking, research work, interest in design and team work, as well as obtaining specific engineering and technological results is observed in the educational systems of many countries of the world. The basis for training specialists in the field of high technologies is STEM education. Currently, STEM education is actively developing as a direction using interdisciplinary and applied approaches, the basic idea of which is the integration of natural sciences, technology, modeling and mathematics. The article presents the importance of the STEM approach in the formation of hard and soft skills for training and professional development, the history of the competence-based approach, classification of key competencies, methods of their formation, the emphasis is placed on the potential of the educational technologies used.

Keywords: competencies, hard skills, soft skills, integration, the potential of educational technologies, project activities, project-based learning.

The main trend taking place in society is associated with the need to develop in the younger generation the skills necessary to live in conditions of uncertainty and rapid change. More and more often, we hear such concepts as skills of the future, digitalization of the economy and education, and recently, an English-language phrase has appeared in the teacher's language - soft skills. This term is quite new for pedagogy, its first use was recorded at the beginning of the last century in the United States. Soft skills were first identified in the study of the competencies of the American military, then the scientists identified two groups of skills: professional and personal. The first group got the name - hard skills, and the second - soft skills. Both of these terms have become widespread, including in the field of education, having become, in essence, a new paradigm for the results of educational activities of students in English-speaking countries on both sides of the Atlantic [1].

The term soft skills currently refers to skills that are common to several types of activities. These include cognitive and intellectual skills, emotional intelligence, the ability to manage one's own activities, and the ability to interact productively with other people. In different publications you can find synonyms for soft skills, for example, «employability skills» (skills for employment), «people skills» (skills to communicate with people), «non-professional skills» (non-professional skills), «key skills», «Skills for social progress» (skills for social development), «life skills» (skills that are necessary in everyday life). Literally translated from English, the term «soft skills» means «soft skills» or «flexible skills», that is, skills that do not belong to the professional field of human activity. The opposite in meaning is the term «hard skills», which translates as «hard» or professional skills. Hard skills, or professional skills, are built on specialization in a profession.

These skills are specific, and when they are mastered, the left hemisphere (logical) of the human brain works more, the average IQ level is important. Soft skills are skills that cannot be confirmed by substantive activity. They are associated with the work of the right (creative) hemisphere of the human brain. Their assimilation requires an IQ level slightly above average [2].

The principle of the 21st century poses new challenges in the world of education, one of the interesting problems is the need for various skills related to adaptation to society. Based on educational outcomes, students should have abilities such as life skills, work skills, applied skills, personal skills, interpersonal skills, and non-cognitive skills. These skills have been around for several decades, but lately, it is increasingly encouraged to teach students these skills at every stage of learning, because success in the modern era requires these 21st century skills.

What does STEM mean in education? STEM education is an approach to teaching and learning that integrates science, technology, engineering, and math as pathways to guide project activities, discussion, and critical thinking. Education experts say STEM education helps students develop the ability to:

- ability to take a well-considered risk;
- participate in meaningful learning activities;
- become resilient problem solvers;
- accept and value collaboration;
- work on the creative process.

STEM teaching allows students to explore thought-provoking questions - types of questions with answers that you cannot simply search the Internet. STEAM is an approach to education that allows students to be curious learners looking for creative solutions to real-world problems; it helps them develop the soft and tough skills they need to succeed in college, their careers, and wherever life takes them. Through the

lens of cooperation and compassion, while at the same time being able to lead their learning [2].

STEM education provides an interdisciplinary learning model where learners can apply content knowledge as well as key skills. A high-quality STEM education prepares graduates to tackle real-world problems with great creativity, critical thinking, and efficiency.

Achievement of this goal encourages scientists and teachers of the country to reform the domestic education system, to significantly update the content and teaching methods. Unfortunately, modern classical education and schools are more focused on the acquisition of knowledge by the student. Students acquire knowledge only for the sake of high marks, and some are not able to master the entire volume of educational material. The content of academic subjects becomes difficult, filled with incomprehensible terminology, abstract concepts.

Therefore, the teachers face the following questions: «How to get the child interested in studying this or that subject?», «How to change the educational process in order to ultimately get a fully gifted personality who, after leaving school, will be able to realize himself?» and there are many such questions. The rapid development of the IT industry, robotics, nanotechnology reveals the need for experienced specialists, which means that there is an acute educational need for high-quality teaching of today's students in technical disciplines - mathematics, physics, engineering, programming. Education should be outstripping, in line with the trends in the development of society in the future.

The widespread introduction of ICT into the educational process requires a certain revision of traditional educational concepts. General application software changes so rapidly that it is impossible to familiarize students with the operation of most software products within a single subject [3].

Computer science, as a school subject, has significant potential for shaping the personality of future citizens. Therefore, it is necessary to teach children not for school, but for life. People who are educated through STEM-based learning are expected to have hard skills that are balanced with soft skills because the learning process is carried out through active learning methods that include communication, collaboration, problem solving, leadership, creativity, and others. Consequently, the STEM teaching model is considered more interesting to learn, due to the awareness of the important role technology and engineering play in the 21st century, they are believed to improve students' soft skills and hard skills [4].

Teaching Based on Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics STEM is an acronym for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics. This acronym was coined by the US National Science Foundation in the 1990s as the theme of the educational reform movement in these four disciplines with the aim of increasing STEM field staff, developing STEM literate citizens, and increasing the global competitiveness of the United States, in scientific and technical innovations.

STEM education is a «meta discipline». The STEM approach is used to advance education in the hope that students will be ready to study the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics in higher education and be able to find future work in the STEM field.

STEM offers an effective way to engage students in high-level thinking and improve problem-solving skills by placing science and math in the context of technology and engineering. The goal of STEM-based learning is to develop skills in science, technology, engineering and mathematics in school graduates. The essence of STEM education is to prepare the 21st century workforce for STEM education and related activities so that students can take lessons in the classroom / laboratory and apply them in real life. The development of STEM-based learning needs to be encouraged and continued to teach effective classroom management so that they can update their knowledge of current trends in STEM education teaching and apply your knowledge to effectively teach students.

Project based learning (PBL) is intertwined with the idea of STEM learning. So: «What is Project Learning»? Project Based Learning (PBL), or Project Based Learning, is an instructional approach designed to empower students to develop knowledge and skills by engaging projects related to problems and challenges they may face in the real world. Because of its focus on 21st century skills, the PBL model also improves the technological ability of students. Project-based learning helps students develop teamwork and problem-solving skills, as well as the ability to communicate effectively with others.

Project-based learning connects students to the world outside the classroom and prepares them to accept and solve problems in the real world in a way that reflects what the professionals do every day. Rather than short-term memorization and summative control, project-based learning empowers students to interact deeply with targeted content, with an emphasis on long-term retention. PBL also improves student attitudes towards education through its ability to keep students engaged. The PBL framework allows for intrinsic motivation as it focuses student learning around a central issue or problem and meaningful outcome. Students ultimately want to understand the answer or solution as much or more than the teacher wants to know what they know, understand, and can do! [5].

Why use PBL as part of a STEM approach?

1. PBL helps students integrate thinking across disciplines.

Great PBL focuses on learning around real-world problems, providing a clear connection between what is being taught in school and how relevant it is outside of the classroom. The authenticity of these problems and questions means that they are complex and confusing, requiring students to draw on disciplinary knowledge and experience in many areas. Innovators in our economy are not confined to one area when they consider these issues; they explore and extract from “scientific, mathematical, artistic, or social elements” solution work.

2. PBL promotes deeper connections to content.

The goal of project learning is not to cover, it is in order to reveal. Project based learning is a research approach that takes time for students to make connections between the problems they face, reflect on what they already know, and develop lines of inquiry for new content they «need to know». This specific context and need for knowledge helps them not only to identify and avoid misconceptions, but also to connect facts and information as they apply knowledge to solve, evaluate and reflect on specific situations [6].

3. PBL develops the research skills needed to be successful in STEM.

An open-minded design approach that does not seek the right answer fosters both the analytical and creative thinking required for innovation. Great project-learning questions don't make students jump into answers, they lead to an even greater increase in the number of questions [6]. For example, a project-based learning approach might ask students to think, «How can we make our cafeteria lunch healthier?» In response, students may ask, «Do you mean healthier for the students, or do you mean healthier for the planet?» Even if students only focus on healthier things for students, they should ask:

- What is the calorie and vitamin content of existing meals?

- Which dinners are your favorites?

- How much lunch do students eat?

- What types of food are thrown away?

4. PBL promotes reflection and metacognition.

The project learning process is recursive and requires a lot of thought in order to successfully design a solution. As students work to develop ideas and implement them, they constantly ask questions such as:

- What do we know? What do we need to know?

- What do I think will happen? Why?

- What really happened? Where did our thinking go wrong?

- What worked? What didn't work?

The reflective nature of the design process helps students make a connection between the content they are learning and how it affects their thinking and problem solving. How well they can find and use this knowledge helps them better understand not only what they are learning, but also how they learn.

Taking a project-based approach to STEM teaching can help students form deeper connections with content, link ideas across disciplines, and develop the questioning, thinking, and metacognitive skills necessary to succeed in today's fast-paced world.

Through hands-on activities, STEM education demonstrates to students the application of scientific and technical knowledge in real life. At each lesson, they get the opportunity to design, build and develop products of the modern industry. By studying a specific project, as a result of which they create a prototype of a real product with their own hands. For example, in the process of creating a robot, students are introduced to concepts such as mobile robots, DC motors, stepper motors, elastic nanotubes, etc.

STEM develops the critical thinking and problem-solving skills needed to overcome the challenges students may face in real life. For example, students develop simple aircraft, then they are tested. After the first test, they reflect and determine the reasons why their aircraft did not reach the finish line. The reasons may be different, the design of the aircraft, the ratio of wings and size, aerodynamics or launch force. After each test, they develop their knowledge and skills to reach the final goal.

By creating various devices, building bridges and roads, launching airplanes and cars, testing robots and electronic games, developing their underwater and air structures, students each time become closer and closer to the goal. They improve their product every time. Ultimately, by solving all the questions and tasks posed, students achieve the final result or goal. Achievement of each goal, in turn, increases students' self-confidence.

A distinctive feature of STEM is also active communication and teamwork. At the stage of discussion, a free atmosphere is created for discussions and expression of opinions. The participants in the discussion and discussion develop skills that allow them to freely express their opinions, as well as present information at the proper level. Active participation in the learning process allows students to master the topic well. Most of the study time is given to active activities such as testing and design development. They communicate with instructors and their teammates all the time, which allows them to develop communication skills in students.

STEM increases the interest of students in their regular classes. For example, in physics lessons, they study the force of gravity of the earth, explain it with formulas on the board, and in STEM circles, school-children can strengthen their knowledge by building and launching parachutes, rockets or airplanes. It is not always easy for students to understand terms that they do not see or hear. For example, pressure or expansion of volume due to an increase in temperature. In STEM classes, they can easily understand these terms through fun experiments. That is why in many countries, secondary schools are actively collaborating with STEM centers.

What soft skills can students develop through STEM classes?

Involving children in STEM classes from an early age not only helps them better understand the world around them, but also has a great impact on the development of their interpersonal skills. Soft skills are just as important as hard skills when it comes to work and life [7]. Collaboration and problem solving are the most in-demand 21st century workplace skills that can be developed with STEM:

Interdisciplinary skills. Let's start with interdisciplinary skills. When children are exposed, get to work, or learn about science, technology, engineering and mathematics, it helps them understand and develop an interdisciplinary teaching method. The interdisciplinary teaching method will also help them understand the real world, based on the fact that the world is complex and confusing [8].

Critical thinking and problem solving. When working with STEM projects, children are encouraged to use their imagination and acquired knowledge to solve problems. They will be directed to think critically, and every time they face a problem or problem, they will analyze the problem and think about possible solutions. This will help children learn to solve problems, and not just give up all the difficulties or problems that they will face in life or in their future workplace.

Creativity. Another very important soft skill that children develop when working with standard projects and activities is creativity.

Hands-on projects allow them to use their creativity and imagination to create projects from the real world and use them for a variety of purposes.

Stability. STEM is all about experimentation, that's how learning happens here. We try to give children the opportunity to experiment, try and learn how things work, all in practice. During the experiments, children will face failure, because everything does not always work out. Thus, children are emotionally and psychologically prepared to cope with setbacks, to keep trying new methods or techniques until they succeed. The ability to cope with setbacks and look for new solutions is a very important and useful skill for everyone throughout life.

Overconfidence. In fact, self-confidence is more of a mindset than a skill. But now, more than ever, with the constant development of all aspects of life, self-confidence is definitely a superpower. When working with children in STEM, one of the best moments is when you see the excitement and confidence that a child can get every time he / she achieves something or completes a project that he / she has been working on.

Communication. Communication is one of the most valuable skills of the 21st century. Children who work together on STEM exercises learn to communicate and formulate ideas in a way that is understandable and easy for others to help bring the idea to life.

Recently, several factors have contributed to the development of STEM education in the secondary education system in Kazakhstan. As part of the renewal of the content of education, the implementation of early education in the basics of natural sciences and information literacy began, in particular, new integrated educational areas appeared according to the State Compulsory Standard of Primary Education. Also, subjects

of the natural and mathematical direction are studied in English in grades 7-9 of the level of basic secondary education in the mode of partial immersion of the language and in grades 10-11 of the level of general secondary education in the mode of complete immersion of the language into the subject. This contributes to the acquisition of new knowledge in the language of the original source and entry into the global scientific community.

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